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BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS IN HEALTH: TRADITIONAL AND COMPLEMENTARY MEDICINES.

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Policy Statement

Although not recent, discussions on Traditional and Complementary Medicine have gained momentum in recent years. Within the World Health Organization (WHO), the topic has been discussed since the late 1960s, when, in the context of analyses of national health systems, it was observed that in many places around the world, therapeutic approaches and practices not recognized by biomedicine (also called Western medicine or conventional medicine) were being used. It was agreed that the term Traditional Medicine encompasses cultural and indigenous therapeutic and care practices; Complementary Medicine is not linked to the tradition of a people but encompasses knowledge and care approaches that, although not fully integrated and recognized in mainstream health systems, are used in a complementary way. The WHO has recommended that its members advance research into the safety and efficacy of such practices, considering, within their capacities, their incorporation as a complement to health services. It is argued that such practices contribute to care from a multidimensional physical, emotional, and spiritual approach to individual needs. Expanding the supply of Traditional and Complementary Medicine has the potential to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), especially regarding Goal 3, which aims to ensure a healthy life and promote well-being for all at all ages..

Background

Care therapeutic approaches vary significantly between countries, and their use depends on culture, understanding, and accessibility. Examples of Traditional Medicine include Acupuncture, Auriculotherapy, and other Traditional Chinese Medicine practices; Ayurveda, a traditional system of medicine originating in India; and Unani Medicine, which encompasses a care system with roots in Greece. Examples of Complementary Practices include Phytotherapy, Homeopathy, Meditation, and Massage Therapy, among others[1]. Over the years, western biomedicine has become hegemonic in the world's health systems, not continuously integrating the traditional or complementary forms of care provided by local communities.

WHO members have been discussing the opportunities and challenges of integrating Traditional and Complementary Medicine (TCM) into national health systems. While the challenge was raised at the 1969 World Health Assembly, it was at the 1978

International Conference on Primary Health Care in Alma-Ata, a Declaration was published recognizing the need to work with multidisciplinary health teams involving doctors, nurses, auxiliaries, and other therapeutic practices to respond to communities' expressed health needs [2]. Within the framework of the WHO, a Program on Traditional Medicine has been established to make progress on the topic.

Over the years, there have been many difficulties in gathering data from the research and identifying the attributes of the different care approaches. In 2001, for example, a report was published. Still, it took ten years to consolidate data on the regulation of practices by member states (both due to the lack of funding and the difficulty of accessing information)[3].

The WHO has been working on learning mechanisms and socializing good practices in this context. It worked on the first global strategy (2002-2005)[4], providing frameworks for action by member states to design their national policies, and on the second global strategy (2014-2023)[5], building on the foundations of its predecessor and deepening support and stimulating the supply of traditional and complementary medicine products, practices and professionals in national health services.

Findings

In WHO discussions, the emphasis has been on understanding the use of traditional and complementary therapeutic approaches to improve how people care for their health. The goal is not to replace conventional medicine but to complement it by integrating care from other epistemologies. One of the most recent reports highlights:

Traditional and complementary medicine (T&CM) is an important and often underestimated health resource with many applications, especially in the prevention and management of lifestyle-related chronic diseases, and in meeting the health needs of ageing populations. Many countries are seeking to expand coverage of essential health services at a time when consumer expectations for care are rising, costs are soaring, and most budgets are either stagnant or being reduced. Given the unique health challenges of the 21st century, interest in T&CM is undergoing a revival (WHO, 2019, p. 5)[6]

The number of countries incorporating national policies on Traditional and Complementary Medicine has shown an upward trend in recent decades (Figure 1). The national policy generally includes defining the government's role, guiding principles on safety and efficacy issues, vision and mission, and goals and objectives.

Figure 1: WHO Member States with National Policies on TCM (1999-2018).

Source: WHO, 2019, p. 15.

The challenge is that these policies are carried out by more than state regulation. Multiple agents are relevant and necessary to stimulate the supply of these practices to the population. Figure 2 indicates that most providers are located within the private sector. This limits the accessibility of TCM therapeutic approaches for a significant portion of the population due to their high costs.

Figure 2: Suppliers of TCM.

Source: WHO, 2019, p. 15.

Conclusions

More results based on scientific evidence are still needed for many therapeutic approaches within the scope of Traditional and Complementary Medicine. There are considerable efforts to advance this field of research worldwide, as well as by the recently established WHO World Center for Traditional Medicine[7].

In any case, health experiences based on other medical rationalities - different from biomedicine or conventional medicine - are considered by the member states and technicians of WHO as relevant approaches to improving the population's health conditions.

There has been a significant increase in the demand for holistic care, which considers individuals in their multiple dimensions (bio-psycho-spiritual) and their interactions with the socio-economic-cultural context in which they live. Thus, conventional medical-centered medicine, focused on disease, is gradually being deconstructed in favor of the advent of integrative, interdisciplinary, holistic medicine, which focuses on health and is based on self-care.

This is, therefore, a change in the paradigm of care, which must be geared towards guaranteeing safety and effectiveness in the practice of traditional therapies, as well as the quality of the training of their practitioners. This process requires a new epistemological outlook, broadening the perspectives of current academicism, but within criteria that consider traditional knowledge, guaranteeing its safety and effectiveness without misconfiguring it from its traditional roots or disregarding the importance of the holders of this knowledge.

Recommendations

The global discussions show local recommendations for three groups: local governments, health professionals, and society.

That the local governments:

Recognize that the population's health is more than the absence of disease. It encompasses access to well-being, and approaches within the scope of Traditional and Complementary Medicines contribute to this.

Implement traditional medicines in their public health systems to guarantee free access for the population.

Support implementation through partnerships with institutions that can act to build evidence maps of results with the use of traditional therapies (universities); with training centers to act in the training of TCM practitioners (considering in this process the holders of ancestral knowledge and health teams working in TCM) and with volunteers to guarantee the supply of TCM to the growing demand for these therapies.

Identify health professionals in the public system who use TCM and promote it to make them political entrepreneurs in this process.

That healthcare professionals:

They should be introduced to TCM through experimentation, as the relationship with these therapies essentially comes from witnessing and feeling their results. It's also essential to encourage this introduction during your undergraduate studies, which is the period when you build your professional profile.

Keep abreast of WHO discussions on TCM. Although a significant proportion of the more conventional health schools erase this knowledge, it is part of national policies with specific regulations.

Engage in research and discussions on these practices, prioritizing local knowledge and recognizing its role in the context of sustainable development goals (SDGs).

Participate and collaborate in the WHO World Center for Traditional Medicine discussions.

That the society:

Be introduced to TCM by experiencing its results through traditional therapy workshops within the public health system and in different community meeting environments (schools, community centers, health councils).

Get involved in the institutionalization of TCM through social groups organized to promote this process, actively contributing to the Sustainable Development Goals.

Contribute with knowledge based on local culture so that the institutionalization of TCM is also a process of social insertion and cultural recognition.

Demand that governments implement policies for access to the TCM approaches and practices.

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